

AI4RIVER: A Web-Based, Multi-Model System for Operational River-Flow Forecasting

Zahra Mardani^{a,1}, Gonçalo Jesus^{a,1,*}, Anabela Oliveira^a, Elsa Alves^a

^a*Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Avenida do Brasil 101, 1700-066 Lisboa, Portugal*

Abstract

Accurate river-flow forecasts are critical for flood mitigation, reservoir management, and water-allocation planning. With monitoring networks, artificial intelligence (AI) has become essential for converting observations into real-time predictions. We present AI4RIVER, a web platform that automates the deep-learning workflow, from station-metadata ingestion and preprocessing to model training and one-click deployment. AI4RIVER integrates three neural architectures MLP, LSTM, and GRU within an intuitive GUI, providing metrics (RMSE) and enabling users to compare model skill. In a 30-year case study on Portugal's Tejo River, the platform produced reliable three-day forecasts comparable to a process-based model, reproducible through point-and-click interaction. Deployed models run as scheduled jobs, publishing forecasts via a REST API with automated PDF/Excel reporting and threshold-based alerting. By abstracting coding tasks and codifying best practices in data handling, model configuration, and deployment, AI4RIVER empowers water-resources managers and flood-mitigation authorities to harness deep learning forecasts without requiring specialised ML expertise or training.

Keywords: River-flow forecasting, Deep learning, LSTM, GRU, Tejo River

*Corresponding author. Email: gjesus@lnec.pt

¹These authors contributed equally to this work.

1. Introduction

Floods are extreme hydrological events that pose significant risks to communities, infrastructures, and ecosystems around the world. Accurate and timely river flow forecasts are indispensable for reservoir operation, flood mitigation planning, and sustainable management of water resources.

Historically, hydrological models based on physical processes, such as the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT; Arnold et al. 2) and Hydrologic Modeling System (HEC-HMS), have been the backbone of river flow prediction. These models solve the equation for the water balance, based on the principle of mass conservation, that includes precipitation, evapotranspiration, infiltration, and channel routing, providing interpretable representations of the underlying processes. However, they require extensive calibration of site-specific parameters, detailed spatial datasets (digital elevation models, land-use maps, soil properties), and manual adjustments when applied to ungauged or poorly monitored basins [8]. The time and expertise required for parameter estimation and sensitivity analysis often limit their rapid deployment in operational contexts.

Over the past decade, data-driven methods, particularly machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), have emerged as competitive alternatives. Recurrent neural networks, such as long-short-term memory (LSTM; Hochreiter and Schmidhuber 12) and gated recurrent units (GRU; Cho et al. 6), excel at capturing temporal dependencies in flow and meteorological time series. Kratzert et al. [17, 19] demonstrated that LSTM models can outperform traditional hydrological models in benchmark basins when long records of high-quality data are available. Other architectures, including multilayer perceptrons (MLPs), convolutional neural networks (CNNs), and hybrid models, have been applied to season-ahead and sub-daily forecasting tasks, frequently reducing error metrics by 10–25% relative to calibrated physical models.

Despite these advances, adoption among non-specialist water managers remains limited due to steep technical barriers. Building an end-to-end DL forecasting pipeline typically requires (1) collecting and aligning heterogeneous station metadata, (2) handling missing or irregularly sampled data, (3) designing and tuning neural architectures, (4) provisioning computational resources for model training, and (5) deploying trained models for real-time inference and alerting. IT platforms can help uptake these technologies by facilitating DL applications, supported by a DL forecasting framework.

Existing code-centric frameworks, such as NeuralHydrology [18], hydroDL

[24], and AI4Water [1], offer powerful APIs but assume proficiency in Python scripting and DevOps practices. In contrast, tools such as DATimeS [3] and HydroEcoLSTM [21] simplify individual steps but typically limit the choice to a single neural network type (often LSTM) and operate only in local desktop environments rather than in scalable cloud infrastructures.

AI4RIVER addresses these limitations by guiding users through a standardized five-step workflow validated in previous studies on MLP-based river-flow forecasting [15] that integrates project and station and controlling variables setup, automated gap-aware preprocessing, multiarchitecture model training, validation dashboards, and one-click deployment of RESTful endpoints with automated reporting and alerting. The web platform currently supports MLP, LSTM, and GRU models, with provisions for adding additional architectures in future updates. Detailed descriptions of each step are provided in Sections 3 and 3.3.

By abstracting coding complexity and embedding best practices in data handling, model selection, and deployment, AI4RIVER enables water resource managers, reservoir operators, and flood mitigation authorities to take advantage of advanced DL forecasting without specialized programming expertise. The remainder of this paper reviews related work (Section 2), the Section 3 shows the features of the web application in detail and presents the mathematical formulations of supported architectures and concludes with a real-world case study of the Tejo River (Section 4.1) followed by a discussion of future developments (Section 5).

2. Related Works

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have become increasingly prominent in hydrological forecasting, leading to the development of two main classes of tools: (1) code-centric research frameworks aimed at expert users and (2) graphical or web-based platforms designed for practitioners without programming experience. In this section, we review both categories, evaluating tools according to the architectures they support, their ability to handle data gaps, ease of use, availability of deployment features (REST, scheduling, alerts), and scalability across multiple stations.

2.1. Research-Grade ML/DL Libraries

Research frameworks provide powerful low-level APIs that support large-scale experimentation and basin-wide studies, but they typically require sub-

stantial programming effort and lack integrated deployment workflows.

NeuralHydrology [18] offers LSTM and community-contributed GRU implementations trained on the CAMELS-US and CAMELS-EU datasets (USGS gauges and NOAA/ERA5 reanalysis). It supports multi-basin experiments over multi-decadal series and excels at batch processing of thousands of catchments. However, it does not provide a graphical interface, does not have built-in scheduling, and GRU support may require extensions.

hydroDL [24] couples USGS streamflow and CHIRPS precipitation to run national-scale LSTM forecasts on HPC clusters or other remote environments. Despite its flexibility, users must manually script gap handling, hyperparameter management, and model deployment.

AI4Water [1] integrates local hydrometric networks and ESA SMOS soil-moisture products into MLP/CNN workflows that span multi-decadal daily data. However, it lacks recurrent architectures, automated scheduling, and alerting out of the box.

HydPy 6.0 [13] enables users to chain SWAT outputs with arbitrary Python-based ML modules for basin-scale studies. Although flexible, it lacks a GUI and cloud-native capabilities.

PyWaterShed [26] exposes a REST API to infer discharge from USGS JSON feeds, enabling the consumption of lightweight models. However, preprocessing, retraining, data alignment, and visualization must be implemented manually by the client.

None of these research-grade libraries provides a fully self-service environment in which non-specialists can configure, train, and deploy basin-specific AI forecasts end-to-end directly from operational monitoring stations.

2.2. Practitioner-Oriented Tools

Tools in this category emphasize usability and accessibility by offering graphical interfaces, but often restrict users to limited model families or lack automated operational features.

DATimeS [3] is a standalone MATLAB toolbox for optical remote-sensing time series. It reads vegetation-index data from raster files or CSV, provides built-in visualization and phenology metrics, and supports multi-year daily LSTM experiments. However, it runs exclusively on the local desktop and provides neither REST endpoints nor cloud-based scheduling.

HydroEcoLSTM [21] is a Python GUI application focused on hydro-ecological modeling based on LSTM using CSV or HDF5 catchment-scale

time series. It offers interactive plots, but does not support other neural architectures or automated deployment.

SMETool [14] provides a browser-based GUI for gradient-boosted precipitation forecasts from regional stations. It omits recurrent networks and automated alerting.

SandTank-ML [11] allows users to experiment with Random Forests and LSTMs on datasets of up to $\sim 10^5$ samples within the browser and export training scripts. Scheduling, notifications, and deployment must be configured manually.

HydroCompute [9] offers WebAssembly-backed JavaScript widgets for interactive forecast visualization using gauge/radar data adapters. Model training occurs on external back ends, and end-to-end automation is not included.

Transform-HydroAPI [22] delivers a SaaS JSON API for inference using pre-deployed models. It does not provide preprocessing, retraining, or user-defined model configurations.

Commercial cloud services such as IBM's *The Weather Company* and AWS Forecast offer global-scale AutoML pipelines with REST endpoints and scheduling, but rely on proprietary datasets and are not tailored to hydrology-specific preprocessing or station-level gap handling.

Table 1: Comparison of representative hydrological forecasting tools

Toolkit	Models & Data	Interface	Limitations
NeuralHydrology [18]	LSTM, GRU on CAMELS-US/EU (USGS + NOAA/ERA5)	Code API	No GUI; no scheduling
hydroDL [24]	LSTM on USGS + CHIRPS	Python scripts	Manual gap handling and deployment
AI4Water [1]	MLP, CNN on local gauges + ESA SMOS	Code API	No RNNs; no alerts/scheduling
HydPy 6.0 [13]	SWAT outputs + custom ML	Python API	No GUI; no cloud integration
PyWaterShed [26]	Discharge from USGS JSON feeds	REST API	No preprocessing, retraining, or visualization
DATimeS [3]	LSTM on vegetation-index time series	Desktop GUI	Single architecture; local only
SMETool [14]	GBDT on regional meteorological stations	Web GUI	No RNNs; no scheduling/alerts
SandTank-ML [11]	RF, LSTM on CSV ($\sim 10^5$ points)	Web GUI + script export	No scheduling or alerts
Transform-HydroAPI [22]	Pre-deployed models (SaaS)	REST API	No preprocessing or retraining
IBM/AWS Forecast	AutoML on proprietary global data	Cloud API + web console	Subscription; not hydrology-specific
AI4RIVER (this work)	MLP, LSTM, GRU on SNIRH/JSON	Web GUI + REST API	End-to-end pipeline for daily, three-day forecasts

To our knowledge, none of the existing tools provides an *on-demand* service that allows users to select operational monitoring stations for a basin of interest and subsequently build, validate, and deploy their own AI-based forecasts with scheduled updates and alerts. **AI4RIVER** fills this gap by combining gap-aware preprocessing, multi-architecture training (MLP/LSTM/GRU), automated deployment, scheduled updates, RESTful delivery, and alerting within a single unified web application.

3. Features of the Web Application

This section outlines the general methodology used for river flow forecasting, adapted and extended from the workflow originally proposed in this paper [15]. That study laid the foundation for a structured deep-learning forecasting pipeline and an accompanying GUI, organized into three key stages: pre-processing, model development, and model validation forecasting.

In this work, we adopt and extend that methodology within the AI4RIVER platform, applying it to real-time forecasting with multiple neural architectures (MLP, LSTM, GRU) and full pipeline automation via a web interface. Each step in the pipeline is adapted to the specific data conditions and the dynamics of the river selected by the user. Figure 1 summarizes the end-to-end forecasting workflow, from data ingestion to multi-horizon forecast output (1-, 2-, and 3-day ahead predictions).

Figure 1: Methodology architecture diagram adapted from [15], expanded for multi-model web-based deployment.

3.1. Deep-Learning Model Formulations

AI4RIVER supports three core architectures for multi-horizon forecasting. Let $\mathbf{x}_t \in \mathbb{R}^d$ denote the d -dimensional input vector (flows, meteorological

covariates) at day t , and \hat{y}_{t+h} the forecast at horizon h .

Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP). We flatten an input window of length p into a vector $\mathbf{h}^{(0)} = \text{vec}(\mathbf{x}_{t:t-p+1})$ and propagate through L fully connected layers:

$$\mathbf{h}^{(\ell)} = \sigma(\mathbf{W}^{(\ell)}\mathbf{h}^{(\ell-1)} + \mathbf{b}^{(\ell)}), \quad \ell = 1, \dots, L-1, \quad \hat{y}_{t+h} = \mathbf{W}^{(L)}\mathbf{h}^{(L-1)} + b^{(L)}.$$

Dropout and regularization ℓ_2 mitigate overfitting [25].

Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM). At each step t , the LSTM maintains a hidden state \mathbf{h}_t and a cell state \mathbf{c}_t through the input, forget, and output gates.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{i}_t &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}_i\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_i\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_i), & \mathbf{f}_t &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}_f\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_f\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_f), \\ \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t &= \tanh(\mathbf{W}_c\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_c\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_c), & \mathbf{c}_t &= \mathbf{f}_t \odot \mathbf{c}_{t-1} + \mathbf{i}_t \odot \tilde{\mathbf{c}}_t, \\ \mathbf{o}_t &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}_o\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_o\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_o), & \mathbf{h}_t &= \mathbf{o}_t \odot \tanh(\mathbf{c}_t), \end{aligned}$$

with final output \hat{y}_{t+h} from a linear projection of \mathbf{h}_t [12].

Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU). The GRU merges forget and input gates into an update gate \mathbf{z}_t and reset gate \mathbf{r}_t :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{z}_t &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}_z\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_z\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_z), & \mathbf{r}_t &= \sigma(\mathbf{W}_r\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_r\mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{b}_r), \\ \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_t &= \tanh(\mathbf{W}_h\mathbf{x}_t + \mathbf{U}_h(\mathbf{r}_t \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1}) + \mathbf{b}_h), & \mathbf{h}_t &= (1 - \mathbf{z}_t) \odot \mathbf{h}_{t-1} + \mathbf{z}_t \odot \tilde{\mathbf{h}}_t, \end{aligned}$$

followed by a linear layer for the forecast [6].

Training Objective. All architectures minimize multi-horizon mean squared error:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta) = \frac{1}{NH} \sum_{t=1}^N \sum_{h=1}^H (y_{t+h} - \hat{y}_{t+h}(\theta))^2,$$

optimized via Adam [16] with early stopping.

Hyperparameters (window length p , layer widths, dropout, learning rate) are exposed in the GUI, enabling rapid benchmarking without code changes.

3.2. Technological Choices and Implementation

AI4RIVER is implemented entirely in Python, using the Django Web framework (views, URL routing, templating, authentication and session management, caching, CSRF protection) to provide a responsive browser interface and a REST API (Figure 2). Data handling and ETL are built on Pandas (time-series ingestion, resampling, merging, interpolation, HTML/Excel export) and NumPy (high-performance numerical arrays). External SNIRH data² are fetched through the `requests` library from a separate SNIRH SQL database and then passed to the ETL pipeline. All cleaned time series are stored as JSON within Django models (covered by Django’s test suite); no other database is used in the pipeline.

Model development and training employ TensorFlow/ Keras (Sequential API; LSTM, GRU, Dense, Dropout; `EarlyStopping`; serialization of the model to `.h5`) together with scikit-learn utilities (`SimpleImputer`,

`train_test_split`, `learning_curve`, `mean_squared_error`) for preprocessing, dataset splitting and evaluation. Visualizations during training and validation use Matplotlib (Agg backend) and Seaborn for static plots, plus Plotly Graph Objects for interactive dashboards. The pillow is used for image tasks such as thumbnail generation and diagram annotation.

Reporting and deployment automation are based on `openpyxl` (via Pandas’ `ExcelWriter`) to produce in-memory `.xlsx` summaries, while Python’s standard library modules (`io`, `os`, `glob`, `re`, `uuid`, `logging`) manage file I/O, pattern matching, unique naming, and centralized logging. Date parsing and range handling use `dateutil` and the built-in `datetime`. The trained models are containerized (Docker) and scheduled as Kubernetes CronJobs triggered by the Django back end, enabling one-click operational deployment with automated PDF/Excel reporting and threshold-based alerting.

Figure 2: High-level system architecture of AI4RIVER (with separate SNIRH SQL database and Django JSON store).

²<https://snirh.apambiente.pt>

3.3. AI4RIVER — End-to-End Workflow

Workflow overview. The AI4RIVER platform follows a structured five-step workflow that guides users from initial configuration to fully operational forecasting of river flow. Each step is organized around a clear *objective*, accompanied by user-facing *actions* on the graphical interface, an automated *processing* performed by the back end, and the generation of intermediate or final *artefacts*. This standardized pipeline ensures transparency, reproducibility, and ease of use in diverse forecasting scenarios. The five main stages are: (1) project setup, (2) data selection, (3) preprocessing, (4) model training, and (5) forecasting and deployment.

Step 1 – Define the project. *Objective:* Initialize a clean workspace for project tracking and reproducibility. A single page form requests only the *Project Type* (currently fixed to time-series forecasting) and a free text *Project Name*. When you press *Save*, AI4RIVER creates a dated folder on the server, writes a JSON header with a UTC timestamp, and advances the progress bar to 20%. Behind the scenes, nothing heavy happens; the platform simply reserves disk space and a clean directory tree so every plot, model, and log produced later can be traced back unambiguously. (Figure 5)

Step 2 – Select data.

Objective: The goal of this step is to define the dataset that will be used for forecasting by selecting the input drivers, the target station, and the time range. Input drivers include hydrometric data, meteorological data or a combination of both sources. This ensures that the system can combine consistent hydrometric and meteorological records into a unified daily time series ready for preprocessing.

Two coordinated views are provided for this selection. On the left, the dropdown menus list all the from both networks available from SNIRH³ together with their declared sampling cadence. Because the present use case focuses on *daily* forecasts, stations with non-daily sampling remain visible for context but are disabled, helping users understand the overall network coverage while clearly indicating which stations are valid for the current run.

On the right, an interactive leaflet map provides a spatial overview of the same stations, allowing users to visually explore basin coverage and select the gauges to be used in the analysis. After choosing meteorological drivers, upstream flow gauges, and the target gauge for prediction, users specify

³<https://snirh.apambiente.pt>

the the intended duration of the forecast operation by setting the start and end-dates of the forecast period and confirm the selection by clicking *Show Combined Table*.

Once confirmed, the platform retrieves the corresponding data from the SNIRH CSV service over HTTPS, merges the time series by date, and flags missing entries with NA. An HTML preview is generated so that data gaps are immediately visible. In the background, a multithreaded fetcher downloads the feeds in parallel, normalizes format inconsistencies, and stores a cached copy for efficient reuse. (Figure 6)

Step 3 – Pre-process. *Objective:* Clean and format the time series into supervised learning tensors. Two date pickers define the *Training* and *Validation* windows. The training period should ideally cover at least twenty consecutive days, as these observations form the 20-day look-back window used by the deep-learning model. The validation period begins immediately afterward and typically spans one to three hydrological years, allowing a reliable assessment of seasonal forecasting skill. When the user adjusts the boundaries, the right-hand plot updates automatically, shading the training interval in blue and the validation interval in gray, while the raw daily curves remain colored. Internally, AI4RIVER re-indexes all variables onto a complete daily calendar, linearly interpolates gaps of up to ten consecutive days, retains longer gaps as NaN, and converts the cleaned dataset into 3-D supervised tensors in which each sample contains the previous twenty days of all drivers and the targets correspond to day +1, +2, and +3. Both the raw and tensorized datasets are stored. (Figure 7)

Step 4 – Train the model. *Objective:* Fit deep learning models and generate evaluation metrics. A slide-out panel exposes all controls to setup the DL model: A user can switch between MLP, LSTM, or GRU; choose the number of layers and neurons per layer; set batch size and epochs (default 20); and press Train. A Keras job starts with the Adam optimizer and early stopping (patience = one-fifth of the epoch count). The loss curve streams live; When training is stopped, three additional charts appear that compare the predicted versus observed flow for days +1, +2 and +3, each annotated with its RMSE. Meanwhile, the system records every hyperparameter, saves the network weights to an .h5 file, and writes a JSON manifest with station identifiers, date windows, and performance scores. (Figure 8)

Hyperparameter Selection Guidelines. To assist non-expert users, AI4RIVER provides a structured yet lightweight procedure to select deep-learning hyperparameters. Instead of exposing the full high-dimensional configuration space, the platform offers a small set of interpretable controls—number of layers, neurons per layer, learning rate, batch size, epochs, and dropout—together with recommended defaults derived from previous basin-scale experiments [15]. These defaults ensure stable training while allowing users to make targeted refinements.

For MLP models, shallow architectures (one to two hidden layers with 50–100 neurons) typically capture most of the variance in daily flow data. LSTM and GRU configurations benefit from larger hidden states (64–128 units) to model multi-day dependencies. The learning rate is set by default to 3×10^{-3} , as higher values may lead to unstable gradients, while batch size defaults to 32 for a balanced trade-off between noise and convergence speed. Early stopping is enabled automatically to prevent overfitting by stopping training when validation loss no longer improves.

Rather than relying on computationally expensive automated hyperparameter searches, the platform encourages rapid comparative benchmarking. Users can train several configurations in succession and compare RMSE across the three forecast horizons, inspect loss curves, and visually assess prediction–observation alignment. This design offers a practical and transparent model-selection workflow that remains accessible to operational users while supporting reproducible experimentation.

Step 5 – Run in real time. *Objective:* Automate real-time forecasts and issue threshold-based alerts. Two prominent actions are available. The *Summarise* produces a single-page PDF containing data ranges, model architecture, and final accuracy. *Deploy* wraps the fetcher, pre-processing routine, 20-day sliding-window logic, and trained network into a Docker image, pushes the image to the internal registry, and registers a Kubernetes `CronJob` that wakes every day at 06:00 UTC, ingests the latest SNIRH readings, generates a fresh three-day forecast, appends that forecast to a dated log, exposes it through a REST endpoint, and issues e-mail or SMS alerts whenever user-defined thresholds are breached. (Figure 9)

Profile & Preferences drawer. Accessible via the cog icon on the left rail, this collapsible panel maintains a live training history (one row per run showing date, architecture, default *10 epochs / 32 batch*, RMSE for each forecast day, and quick actions to download, launch real-time inference,

or delete) and stores user-defined defaults—home catchment and favorite stations, preferred units and color palette, gap-filling rules, hyperparameter presets, and alert contacts. With these saved choices, an expert user can create, train, and deploy a new daily forecast in under a minute. (Figure 3)

Training History

Date	Model Type	Neurons (Layer 1)	Neurons (Layer 2)	Epochs	Batch Size	RMSE (Day 1)	RMSE (Day 2)	RMSE (Day 3)	Download Model
20250331092544	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331092546	MLP	90	90	100	32	7.727062361334558	6.083996601612915	6.920505637951038	Download
20250331092714	GRU	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331092716	GRU	90	90	100	32	3.5795090842773156	1.6698140070470402	2.7214046102469474	Download
20250331092814	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331092815	MLP	90	90	100	32	7.728195526998241	6.083996601612915	6.916004317715269	Download
20250331093852	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331093854	MLP	90	90	100	32	156.7573450731257	227.0153663576543	228.7679552379441	Download
20250331094822	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331094825	MLP	90	90	100	32	159.89470412196272	228.67064026400504	231.96305605634703	Download
20250331100056	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331100059	MLP	90	90	100	32	154.6427460511808	225.78445715715242	231.24104712399136	Download
20250331100643	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331100646	MLP	90	90	100	32	163.4763338185378	230.16949427269896	228.4462720613974	Download
20250331101028	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331101030	MLP	90	90	100	32	156.34284116765627	230.19326119589167	236.63314665056964	Download
20250331102608	MLP	90	90	100	32				Download
20250331102611	MLP	90	90	100	32	157.63773739178066	228.04772663852626	229.63705228305383	Download

Figure 3: Profile Preferences drawer showing saved defaults and training history for quick forecast deployment.

4. Practical application

4.1. Case study: Tejo River

The Tagus basin (Figure 4) is the largest in the Iberian Peninsula, draining 80 626 km²—about one quarter of which lies in Portugal—and stretching 1007 km from its Spanish headwaters to the Atlantic. Flow regulation is dominated by a cascade of reservoirs on both the main stem and its tributaries, so controlled releases - rather than rainfall alone - govern downstream discharge patterns [10]. Historic floods (e.g., 1978, 1979, 1989, 1996, 2013, 2016) underline the need for robust forecasts, while the estuarine reaches near Lisbon demand tight management of the freshwater–saltwater balance [23].

For this study, we assembled daily time series of dam outflows and precipitation spanning 1 October 1984 to 26 September 2023 at key control points (Fratel, Castelo de Bode, and Almourol). These records feed directly into the AI4RIVER workflow demonstrated below to predict daily river flow at the *Almourol* station.

Figure 4: Hydrometric network in the Tagus basin.

4.1.1. Detailed Walk-Through of Use Case

Step 1 – Project setup. The operator selects time series forecast and names the project Tejo_Dam_MLP. A dated workspace folder is created and the progress bar advances to 20%. The project identifier (slug) is reused in the deployment dashboard and in REST endpoints for traceability. The interface for this step is shown in Figure 5.

Step 2 – Data selection. Fratel and Castelo de Bode are chosen as input stations, and Almourol is chosen as the prediction target for a daily forecast of three days (with a 20-day delay). The time span is set to 1984–2025⁴. After clicking *Show Combined Table*, the merged daily data set is displayed with missing values highlighted for quick inspection. All SNIRH,⁵ stations

⁴ensure that this range is consistent with the extent of the data set stated above.

⁵<https://snirh.apambiente.pt>

Figure 5: Step 1 – Project setup screen with project type and name; the project ID is carried forward to deployment and API endpoints.

are visible with their native cadence for situational awareness; this experiment proceeds only in the daily subset. The selection and preview screen is illustrated in Figure 6.

Step 3 – Pre-processing. Training (1984-2022) and validation (Jan. 2025) windows are defined with date pickers. A dual plot updates live, shading training in blue and validation in gray while showing colored daily flow curves. Gaps up to 10 consecutive days are interpolated; longer gaps remain as NaN. The cleaned frame is reshaped into supervised samples using a 20-day look-back to predict the next three days. This configuration is shown in Figure 7.

Step 4 – Model training. An MLP with two hidden layers of 90 neurons (tanh) is trained for 100 epochs, batch size 32, Adam with a learning rate $\eta = 3 \times 10^{-3}$, and early stopping (patience 15). A live loss curve is displayed; upon completion, metrics per horizon (day +1, +2, +3) are reported. For this Tejo case study, the training window covered October 1984 to December 2024, while the validation period spanned from 1 January 2025 to 7 April 2025. Over this validation set, the model achieved RMSE values of 170.97 for Day 1, 299.71 for Day 2, and 368.29 for Day 3 forecasts, showing strong skill for near-term horizons and a gradual increase in error with longer lead times. The trained weights (.h5) and a JSON manifest (hyperparameters, station IDs, date windows, scores, fixed random seed) are saved for full reproducibility. The training interface and output are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 6: Step 2 – Data selection (maps and lists) and combined daily table preview for the Tejo case (Fratel, Castelo de Bode → Almourol).

Figure 7: Step 3 – Pre-processing: window definition, gap handling (10-day max interpolation), and supervised framing (20-day lag, 3-day horizon).

Figure 8: Step 4 – MLP training view with live loss and horizon-wise diagnostics; artefacts (weights and manifest) are versioned and timestamped.

Step 5 – Forecasting & deployment. A summary report can be generated or the model can be deployed. The deployment enables scheduled daily forecasting from updated SNIRH feeds and also supports on-demand runs from the dashboard. Outputs are logged, exposed through an REST endpoint, and alerts are raised when thresholds are exceeded; a recent RMSE appears on the live deployments page.

Figure 9: Step 5 – Deployment screen offering scheduled (06:00 UTC) and on-demand forecasts, REST publication, logging, and alert configuration.

In addition, the system generates a real-time forecast table that displays predicted flows for the next three days, which is available both in the Web interface and in downloadable Excel format. For example, on 8 April 2025, the model issued predictions of 1205.5, 1164.1, and 1070.9 m³/s for 8, 9, and 10 April, respectively. This table provides an immediate, operator-friendly view of upcoming river conditions, complementing the graphical plots and REST API outputs. The deployment view is shown in Figure 9.

4.2. Strengths and Limitations

Building and operating a web-based deep learning platform such as platform such as AI4RIVER involves a sequence of non-trivial tasks. Data handling comes first: The system must ingest and align heterogeneous time series (hydrometric flows, meteorological observations, satellite-derived variables), interpolate short gaps, and normalize inputs without manual effort

[17, 24]. Model development then requires intuitive control over hyperparameters (learning rate, batch size, architecture depth/width, regularization), while efficient search over this high-dimensional space benefits from grid/random/Bayesian strategies [4] and experiment tracking for comparison and reproducibility [27]. On the back end, training must be orchestrated across available compute (CPU/GPU/serverless) with scheduling and quotas to remain responsive [5]. Once trained, models need to be serialized and served with low latency; containerization and caching reduce cold-start costs for both scheduled and on-demand inference [20]. Reliability also depends on the versioning of every artifact, data preparation settings, hyperparameters, and weight snapshots, and on continuous monitoring of forecast skills and pipeline health to detect drift or failure [7]. These capabilities are surfaced through a GUI that provides live loss curves, multi-horizon error metrics, and interactive time-series plots, enabling operation without code.

The current release has clear strengths: an end-to-end, gap-aware pipeline (data ingestion \rightarrow preprocessing \rightarrow multi-model training \rightarrow one-click deployment), support for three neural families (MLP, LSTM, GRU), reproducible runs via time-stamped manifests, REST endpoints for programmatic access, and both scheduled (06:00 UTC) and on-demand forecasts. At the same time, limitations remain: the workflow targets daily cadence only; uncertainty quantification is deterministic (no probabilistic intervals or ensembles); gap filling is linear and capped at 10 consecutive days; physics constraints are not yet embedded; and performance depends on the availability and quality of upstream station metadata. These trade-offs guide the roadmap outlined in Section 5.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

AI4RIVER showcases how a fully integrated web-based platform can make state-of-the-art deep learning models for river flow forecasting accessible and operational. By automating the entire process, from collecting and preparing data to training, testing, launching the model, and sending alerts, AI4RIVER connects hydrological research with real-time decision-making. The platform allows water managers to set up, test and use predictive models without needing to write any code, thanks to its support for different types of neural networks (MLP, LSTM, GRU), handling of missing data, and scheduled forecasts using a computer. The case study on Portugal’s Tejo River confirms the ability of the platform to deliver reliable forecasts

three days in advance, highlighting its value for flood mitigation, reservoir management, and operational water planning. In addition, AI4RIVER promotes reproducibility through versioned outputs and standardized pipelines, providing a solid foundation for transparent and auditable AI applications in hydrology. As environmental conditions become increasingly dynamic, tools like AI4RIVER represent a critical step toward modern, responsive, and data-driven water resource management.

We will enhance AI4RIVER to deal with various temporal resolutions, progressing beyond daily predictions to include sub-daily (e.g., minute- and hourly-based) as well as seasonal and yearly forecasting processes. This temporal flexibility allows the system to adjust to both rapidly shifting hydrological events, such as flash floods, and gradual processes, such as drought progression or long-term reservoir management. The preprocessing pipeline will be adjusted to ingestion, alignment, and resampling various time series across various cadences while preserving temporal consistency and data integrity. Furthermore, we will include additional datasets designed for different prediction horizons. High-frequency precipitation data from radar mosaics or dense gauge networks will enhance short-term forecasts, while reanalysis fields, reservoir operating records, and physiological characteristics will enhance long-range forecasting and geographic generalization. The modeling engine will be upgraded to integrate advanced deep learning methodologies, such as Temporal Convolutional Networks (TCNs) for effective long-term dependency capture, transformer-based architectures for multi-horizon sequence-to-sequence learning, and Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) that leverage spatial relationships among stations. These models will be included in a cohesive automated training and deployment pipeline, enabling practitioners to seamlessly transition between architectures according to their particular use cases. In addition, uncertainty quantification techniques, such as deep ensembles or quantile-based losses, will be included to guaranty resilient decision-making across all temporal dimensions.

Software and data availability

Software. The AI4RIVER web platform used in this study was developed at LNEC and is available for public use through the portal <https://ai4river-portal.lnec.pt>. Users can configure projects, select stations, train models and obtain operational forecasts directly in the browser at no

cost. The underlying source code is currently hosted on internal LNEC servers and is not distributed as open-source software.

Hydrometric and meteorological data. Daily discharge, dam-release and precipitation time series were obtained from the Portuguese National Water Resources Information System (SNIRH, <https://snirh.apambiente.pt>), which is openly accessible to all users. The Tejo case study uses daily records from the Fratel, Castelo de Bode and Almourol stations over 1 October 1984–26 September 2025, as detailed in Section 4.1. These series can be downloaded directly from SNIRH using the station identifiers and date ranges reported in this paper.

Author contributions

Conceptualization, G. Jesus and Z. Mardani; Methodology, G. Jesus, Z. Mardani and E. Alves; Software, Z. Mardani; Validation, G. Jesus, Z. Mardani, E. Alves and A. Oliveira; Investigation, G. Jesus, Z. Mardani and E. Alves; Data curation, Z. Mardani and E. Alves; Writing – original draft, G. Jesus, Z. Mardani and E. Alves; Writing – review & editing, G. Jesus, Z. Mardani and A. Oliveira; Project administration, A. Oliveira; Funding acquisition, A. Oliveira. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

This research was supported by funding from the CONNECT project, funded by the Copernicus Marine Service User Engagement Programme 2022–2028; from the INFLOOD project (2024.07287.IACDC), funded by Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT); and from the ATTRACT-DIH project (Digital Innovation Hub for Artificial Intelligence and High-Performance Computing), funded by the Digital European Programme under Grant Agreement 101083770 and the Recovery and Resilience Plan (PRR) within the scope of the Recovery and Resilience Mechanism (MRR) of the European Union (EU), framed in the Next Generation EU, for the period 2021–2026, within project ATTRACT, reference 774. This work used results produced with the support of the Portuguese National Grid Initiative.

Declaration of competing interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Declaration of generative AI

During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT (OpenAI) to assist with language editing, improving clarity, and rephrasing parts of the manuscript text. After using this tool, the authors carefully reviewed and edited all content, and take full responsibility for the accuracy and integrity of the published paper.

References

- [1] Abbas, A., Boithias, L., Pachepsky, Y., Kim, K., Chun, J.A., Cho, K.H., 2022. Ai4water v1.0: An open-source python package for modelling hydrological time series using data-driven methods. *Geoscientific Model Development* 15, 3021–3043.
- [2] Arnold, J.G., Srinivasan, R., Muttiah, R.S., Williams, J.R., 1998. Large-area hydrologic modelling and assessment, part i: Model development. *Journal of the American Water Resources Association* 34, 73–89.
- [3] Belda, M., Tomáš, R., Janeček, M., 2020. DATimeS—an open-source toolbox for vegetation phenology analysis. *Ecological Informatics* 59, 101138.
- [4] Bergstra, J., Yamins, D., Cox, D.D., 2013. Making a science of model search: Hyperparameter optimization in hundreds of dimensions for vision architectures, in: *Proceedings of the 30th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, pp. 115–123. URL: <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v28/bergstra13.html>.
- [5] Burns, B., Grant, B., Oppenheimer, D., Brewer, E., Wilkes, J., 2016. Borg, omega, and kubernetes. *Communications of the ACM* 59, 50–57. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2890784>, doi:10.1145/2890784.

- [6] Cho, K., van Merriënboer, B., Gulcehre, C., Bahdanau, D., Bougares, F., Schwenk, H., Bengio, Y., 2014. Learning phrase representations using RNN encoder–decoder for statistical machine translation, in: EMNLP 2014, pp. 1724–1734.
- [7] Christmann, A., Manske, P., Reininghaus, J., 2021. Monitoring ml systems: A practical guide to evaluating data, models, and prediction quality. Towards Data Science URL: <https://towardsdatascience.com/monitoring-ml-systems-a-practical-guide-72f2b8e5c64e.medium.com>.
- [8] Dunne, T., Leopold, L.B., 2012. Water in Environmental Planning. 3rd ed., W. H. Freeman.
- [9] Erazo, B., Sosa, J., Pizarro, R., 2024. HydroCompute: Browser-based high-performance hydrological computation using webassembly. Environmental Modelling & Software 173, 105638.
- [10] Fernández-Nóvoa, D., Ramos, A.M., González-Cao, J., García-Feal, O., Catita, C., Gómez-Gesteira, M., Trigo, R.M., 2024. How to mitigate flood events similar to the 1979 catastrophic floods in the lower tagus. Nat. Hazards Earth Syst. Sci. 24, 609–630. URL: <https://doi.org/10.5194/nhess-24-609-2024>, doi:10.5194/nhess-24-609-2024.
- [11] Gallagher, L.K., et al., 2021. SandTank-ML: An educational tool at the interface of hydrology and machine learning. Water 13, 3328.
- [12] Hochreiter, S., Schmidhuber, J., 1997. Long short-term memory. Neural Computation 9, 1735–1780.
- [13] HydPy Development Team, 2024. HydPy 6.0: An extensible python framework for terrestrial hydrology. SoftwareX 20, 101320.
- [14] Jarray, A., et al., 2022. SMETool: A web-based machine-learning tool for soil-moisture estimation. Computers & Geosciences 160, 105203.
- [15] Jesus, G., Mardani, Z., Alves, E., Oliveira, A., 2025. Deep learning-based river flow forecasting with mlps: Comparative exploratory analysis applied to the tejo and the mondego rivers. Sensors 25, 2154. doi:10.3390/s25072154.

- [16] Kingma, D.P., Ba, J., 2015. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization, in: ICLR 2015. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1412.6980>.
- [17] Kratzert, F., et al., 2019. Toward improved predictions in ungauged basins: Exploiting the power of machine learning. *Water Resources Research* 55, 11344–11364.
- [18] Kratzert, F., et al., 2022. NeuralHydrology—a python library for deep-learning research in hydrology. *Journal of Open Source Software* 7, 4050.
- [19] Kratzert, F., et al., 2024. Benchmarking sequence-to-sequence and attention architectures for large-scale stream-flow forecasting. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* 28, 223–247.
- [20] Liaw, R., Liang, E., Nishihara, R., Moritz, P., Gonzalez, J.E., Stoica, I., 2018. Tune: A research platform for distributed model selection and training. arXiv preprint URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1807.05118>, arXiv:arXiv:1807.05118.
- [21] Nguyen, H.T., et al., 2025. HydroEcoLSTM: A desktop gui for hydro-ecological forecasting with lstm networks. *Journal of Hydrologic Engineering* 30, 04024089.
- [22] Pulla, S., et al., 2024. Transforming hydrology python packages into web apis for cross-platform forecasting. *Environmental Modelling & Software* 175, 105712.
- [23] Rodrigues, M., Cravo, A., Freire, P., Rosa, A., Santos, D., 2020. Temporal assessment of the water quality along an urban estuary (tagus estuary, portugal). *Marine Chemistry* 223, 103824. doi:10.1016/j.marchem.2020.103824.
- [24] Shen, C., et al., 2020. hydroDL: A python package for deep-learning applications in hydrology. *Journal of Hydrology* 590, 125–235.
- [25] Srivastava, N., Hinton, G., Krizhevsky, A., Sutskever, I., Salakhutdinov, R., 2014. Dropout: A simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 15, 1929–1958.
- [26] USGS Water Resources, 2024. PyWaterShed v0.4—an open-source toolkit for watershed modelling. Computer software. <https://github.com/USGS-R/pww>.

- [27] Zaharia, M., Chen, A., Davidson, A., Ghodsi, A., Hong, M., Konwinski, A., Xin, R., 2018. Accelerating the machine learning lifecycle with mlflow. Data + AI Summit , 1-7URL: <https://mlflow.org/docs/latest/>.